

ТАДҚИҚОТ ВА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

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YULDASHEV Otabek Abduganievich

*(PhD), Associate Professor,
Languages and preschool education faculty,
Tashkent institute of economics and pedagogy,
Chirchik, 111700, Uzbekistan*

IBRAGIMOVA Dilbar Atkhamovna

*Senior teacher,
Languages and preschool education faculty,
Tashkent institute of economics and pedagogy,
Chirchik, 111700, Uzbekistan*

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EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL TOOLS AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR ENHANCING LANGUAGE LEARNING SKILLS

ANNOTATION

This article investigates the significance of digital tools and applications in the enhancement of language learning skills, underscoring their capacity to foster engaging and personalized educational experiences. By analyzing a range of resources, including language learning applications, podcasts, video conferencing tools, and speech recognition software, the paper illustrates how these technologies promote active participation, enhance learner confidence, and create opportunities for authentic communication. The integration of these technologies not only aids students in developing their language proficiency but also equips them with the skills necessary to effectively utilize technology in both educational and professional contexts.

Key words: AI-powered technologies, cloud-based tools, linguistic knowledge, collaborative, language proficiency, digital tools, socio-emotional barriers, communicative competence, sociolinguistic;

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ДЛЯ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ НАВЫКОВ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЯЗЫКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье исследуется значение цифровых инструментов и приложений для совершенствования навыков изучения языка, подчеркивается их способность способствовать получению увлекательного и персонализированного образовательного опыта. Анализируя ряд ресурсов, включая приложения для изучения языка, подкасты, средства видеоконференцсвязи и программное обеспечение для распознавания речи, авторы статьи показывают, как эти технологии способствуют активному участию, повышают уверенность учащихся и создают возможности для аутентичного общения. Интеграция этих технологий не только помогает студентам в развитии их языковых навыков, но и дает им навыки, необходимые для эффективного использования технологий как в образовательном, так и в профессиональном контексте.

Ключевые слова: технологии на базе искусственного интеллекта, облачные инструменты, лингвистические знания, сотрудничество, владение языком, цифровые инструменты, социально-эмоциональные барьеры, коммуникативная компетентность, социолингвистические;

РАҚАМЛИ ВОСИТАЛАР ВА ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ ТИЛ ЎРГАНИШ КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИ ОШИРИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақола тил ўрганиш кўникмаларини оширишда рақамли воситалар ва иловаларнинг аҳамиятини ўрганади, уларнинг қизиқарли ва шахсийлаштирилган таълим тажрибаларини ривожлантириш имкониятларини таъкидлайди. Тил ўрганиш дастурлари, подкастлар, видеоконференцалоқа воситалари ва нутқни аниқлаш дастурлари каби бир қатор манбаларни таҳлил қилиб, ушбу технологиялар қандай қилиб фаол иштирок этишни рағбатлантириши, ўқувчиларнинг ишончини ошириши ва ҳақиқий мулоқот учун имкониятлар яратишини кўрсатади. Ушбу технологияларнинг интеграцияси нафақат талабаларга тилни билишларини ривожлантиришга ёрдам беради, балки уларни таълим ва касбий шароитларда технологиядан самарали фойдаланиш учун зарур бўлган кўникмалар билан таъминлайди.

Калит сўзлар: сунъий интеллектга асосланган технологиялар, булутга асосланган воситалар, лингвистик билимлар, ҳамкорлик, тилни билиш, рақамли воситалар, ижтимоий-эмоционал тўсиқлар, коммуникатив компетенция, социолингвистик;

Introduction:

Modern education is heavily reliant on technology, which has transformed conventional teaching techniques and provided fresh approaches to language learning in the digital age. A revolutionary trend in language education is the incorporation of digital tools and applications to enhance language learning abilities. A variety of digital tools give students the chance to practice these abilities in relevant, real-world situations, including podcasts, video conferencing platforms, speech recognition software, and language learning applications. A few facts regarding digital tools for online education are provided in this article. Teachers started using online instruction as a blended learning strategy during the pandemic.

A portion of these sections deal with the platform, while others deal with the Zoom classes. A description of how these websites and instructional techniques can be used by educators and students to improve the learning process is provided. The article's main section offers and explores pedagogical suggestions for using digital tools to teach listening skills. Every Webpage has advantages and disadvantages for both teachers and students to use. These are the issues we will look at in our piece and offer some solutions for:

- to illustrate how the proper integration of digital tools into the language learning process can greatly improve the learning skills and provide a more accessible and immersive language learning environment;

- to investigate the effects and efficacy of digital tools on language learning abilities, looking at the advantages of using these tools, such as improved learner engagement, increased flexibility, and chances for practice outside of the classroom;

Materials and methods

It also offers ways to maximize their use in language education while addressing potential drawbacks like technology constraints and the requirement for teacher preparation. This article illustrates how digital tools can change language teaching and learning in a digitally connected world by examining research studies and real-world applications. These tools not only improve resource accessibility but also enable personalized, immersive learning experiences.

For instance, learners have the opportunity to listen to authentic audio materials, such as podcasts or videos, thereby enhancing their listening comprehension and exposing them to diverse accents and speech patterns. Furthermore, apps with speech recognition features allow learners to practice pronunciation and fluency while receiving instant feedback, enabling them to refine their speaking abilities over time. Technology has a significant impact on the teaching of foreign languages. Nonetheless, in order to fully realize their potential and exert a favorable influence on the acquisition of foreign language skills, it is imperative that they incorporate an enhanced pedagogical value into their classroom practice.

This article discusses ways in which today's digital technologies, including emerging artificial intelligence tools, can be used in formal learning environments to foster foreign language proficiency. It focuses on the development of students' linguistic knowledge as well as their reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills. Furthermore, it outlines some ongoing challenges to the application of digital technologies in foreign language teaching and learning ways in which teachers and learners can be supported to take advantage of these tools. Numerous different digital technologies can help students develop linguistic knowledge. Developing linguistic competence, which includes knowledge and skills related to grammar and vocabulary, is required for reading, listening, speaking, and writing in a foreign language. It is a crucial foundation of foreign language teaching and learning. It can be developed directly through the teaching of linguistic forms or indirectly through communication-focused tasks that develop linguistic knowledge [1].

In this regard, the utilization of technology in foreign language learning has advanced significantly since its initial emphasis on drill and repetition methods. Game-based platforms and applications today can help teachers and learners implement good practices like interleaving and feedback. Teachers are free to choose from ready-made quizzes or create their own. As these platforms increasingly adopt AI-powered technologies, quizzes can adapt to students' different foreign language proficiency levels and provide personalized feedback, targeted practice, and reinforcement based on individual student's needs. Technology has greatly improved the use of foreign language learning since its initial focus on drill and repeat approaches. Today's game-based platforms and applications can assist educators and learners in implementing effective practices, such as interleaving and providing feedback. Teachers have the option of choosing from a pre-designed quiz or creating their own.

As these platforms continue to adopt AI-powered technologies, quizzes will be able to adapt to students diverse foreign language proficiency levels, providing personalized feedback, targeted practice, and reinforcement based on individual students' requirements. From the 1980s, when the communicative language teaching approach began to take hold, technology struggled to remain relevant until technological breakthroughs in the 1990s. The proliferation of multimedia technologies, the Internet, and personal computers equipped with word processing tools has facilitated the practice of listening and enhanced the availability of non-pedagogical texts in the target language. In the 2000s, the arrival of more interactive and collaborative Web 2.0 technologies, such as discussion forums, blogs, wikis, and later cloud-based tools, accelerated this further¹.

Furthermore, output-oriented media channels like YouTube allowed students to become creators of foreign languages instead of simply consumers. Today, the emergence of AI-powered technologies presents an opportunity for a novel initiative in this direction, one that is more focused on personalized learning. The utilization of resource technologies, such as online dictionaries, translators, or grammar checkers, has the potential to enhance linguistic proficiency. Due to the wealth of contextual information they provide, online dictionaries can facilitate vocabulary acquisition and more successful language use. Through technology that helps analyze texts, students can look for specific words and patterns, or pull vocabulary lists that indicate how words are used in different contexts.

Many foreign language learners today consider such tools to be an essential part of their language learning. Text-based generative AI can take resource technologies another step further by providing a one-stop shop for learners.

ChatGPT, for example, can provide students with contextualized vocabulary definitions and allow them to ask follow-up questions, including in their first language. Additionally, it can generate sample sentences and additional meanings, identify parts of speech, and produce vocabulary notes and explanations of words and phrases to accompany the generated text. In this manner, artificial intelligence tools can aid educators in ensuring that their lesson planning aligns with a diverse range of learning objectives and enhances students' proficiency in foreign languages. The use of digital technologies to support the development of linguistic knowledge can also foster foreign language reading proficiency.

In numerous ways, the act of reading in a foreign language bears resemblance to reading in the learner's native language, as it involves the teaching of similar reading techniques, such as utilizing prior knowledge and inferring, thereby expediting students' progress in both languages. However, it is important to develop linguistic knowledge in order to make progress in reading. Research suggests that first-language cognitive abilities cannot be transferred until a certain proficiency threshold is reached in the foreign language.

However, the Internet provides learners with easy access to nearly endless reading material in foreign languages at all levels. Several studies have demonstrated that the extensive variety of materials accessible can entice foreign language learners to engage in more extensive reading, thereby enabling them to access texts of a higher level than those typically encountered in a classroom setting. Certain students perceive reading on digital or mobile devices as more engaging, more convenient, and more accessible compared to reading printed texts. Furthermore, research indicates that certain features specific to digital texts make reading them more beneficial to foreign language students than paper-based texts.

For example, the availability of additional information and online glossaries or dictionaries can support the development of reading comprehension. Particularly, the ease of access to these tools in comparison to paper-based versions can increase students' motivation to use them, ultimately improving their reading skills. Furthermore, it has been shown that the use of multimedia texts that combine image, audio and text – an approach that digital technologies facilitate – has been particularly effective. Reading in a foreign language no longer needs to be a solitary activity, thanks to collaborative and interactive digital tools. The interactive reading that often occurs on social media platforms, blog sites, wikis, or chat rooms can help learners share the cognitive load of interpreting foreign language texts.

Numerous studies have demonstrated that these tools have a favorable effect on the reading comprehension of learners. Furthermore, by establishing communities of learners, technology can enhance the social aspect of learning, enhance goal orientation, drive, and perseverance, and facilitate more efficient learning methodologies. However, it appears that students' perceptions of these approaches are mediated by their foreign language proficiency, with advanced students reporting more positive attitudes.

The development of AI-powered technologies is bringing new opportunities for the development of reading and other communicative skills within foreign language learning. Text-based generative AI has the potential to assist educators in producing a diverse range of text types for their students, which can then be tailored to cater to their diverse foreign language proficiency levels. This provides students with a wider variety of suitable reading material than is usually available within textbooks. Moreover, artificial intelligence is capable of effortlessly generating comprehension and expansion inquiries, whether they are open-ended or multiple-choice.

Technology's primary value when it comes to listening skills is in facilitating access to pedagogical and non-pedagogical listening material on a range of topics relevant to students' lived experiences. In particular, the Internet has witnessed an explosion in the availability of such content, and the multimedia materials typically found online can foster deeper processing. This enhanced accessibility extends beyond the classroom, enabling students to practice their language learning abilities outside of the classroom, thereby enhancing their level of autonomy. Certain digital tools may also help students notice particular linguistic features or provide an explanation of the appropriate meaning of phrases within a specific context.

Furthermore, digital technology facilitates teachers' capability to create, edit, and publish their own listening resources for a specific purpose or student need. This could include audio texts designed for more focused listening exercises or for improving comprehension of different accents and multi-speaker dialogue. It could also include multiple listening texts with similar content at different foreign language proficiency levels in order to support differentiation. Emerging AI voice generators allow teachers to quickly turn text into speech in different accents and languages, further facilitating this process.

Digital tools also allow teachers to annotate video content with questions, comments, and comprehension checks to create more exciting and interactive listening activities. Teachers are therefore able to design activities that go beyond traditional test-style approaches and are less dependent on foreign language listening exercises developed by textbook publishers.

In the field of communicative language teaching, learners are not only provided with the opportunity to speak a foreign language, but also provided with the necessary support to enhance their language proficiency through spoken communication. Speaking competence encompasses proficiency in both spoken production and spoken interaction, as well as fluency, intelligibility, and self-correction. Video conferencing can facilitate different types of interactions, which can help students develop their spoken language.

The most obvious approach is to encourage learners to communicate with each other through video technology, which provides them with additional time to enhance their spoken language proficiency compared to face-to-face lessons. This is important because limited class time is a common challenge among foreign language teachers in general, and with regards to developing speaking skills specifically. This type of interaction has been shown to improve spoken fluency and reinforce course content learning. Furthermore, establishing a learning community through video conferencing helps overcome some of the socio-emotional barriers to speaking a foreign language such as anxiety and embarrassment.

This type of video conferencing has the potential to facilitate virtual language exchanges, providing learners from diverse geographical and cultural backgrounds with authentic and purposeful interactions in the target language. Research has highlighted the positive impact virtual exchanges can have on functional, sociolinguistic, grammatical, and strategic communicative competences as well as intercultural ones. Virtual approaches offer a viable alternative to physical mobility for students who face physical, financial, and other resource limitations. They have received considerable political support and financial investment from certain national and international authorities in the last decade. Furthermore, digital tools have the potential to facilitate spoken production activities, enabling students to effortlessly create their own audio and/or visual content in a foreign language and disseminate it to a wide audience.

Results and discussion

Language is a means of communication, which helps members of a community communicate and interact with one another. This includes both verbal and nonverbal communication. Language focuses on listening and reading, which can be described as passive or receptive skills, while speaking and writing can be described as active or productive skills. Listening is an essential skill for learning a language. The process of learning a language starts with listening and ends up in the production of writing. After birth, a child is capable of hearing a variety of sounds and distinguishing between them. Every language has a common, natural sequence for the development of language skills. Listening and speaking are often taught together, but beginners should be given more listening than speaking practice. It is imperative to speak at a natural pace, although inexperienced individuals may require some slowing down. It is possible to improve the comprehension of a language by simplifying vocabulary, using shorter sentences, and increasing the number and length of pauses in speech. The significance of listening in language learning and teaching is imperative for language teachers to assist their students in becoming proficient listeners. In the communicative approach to language teaching, this means modeling listening strategies and providing listening practice in authentic situations, such as those learners are likely to encounter when they use the language outside of the classroom.

W.Goh said that, comparing with other skills, there are fewer insights about the process of listening and the way it is learnt. Similarly, D. Richards stated that there exists limited direct research on the comprehension of listening in second language. As for that, we are doing this research not only to help students with better listening, but also to contribute a small part to enrich the listening research that has been done so far. Currently, it is recommended to study not only grammar but also fundamental skills in order to acquire proficiency in foreign languages. In order to enhance our listening abilities, numerous websites are readily available for our use today. For example, to develop listening and pronunciation, we can use the following web pages as an example:

- Randall's ESL Cyber Listening Lab;
- YouGlish;
- News in levels.

Randall's ESL Cyber Listening Lab provides a way for ESL students to improve their listening skills outside of the classroom by providing autonomous learning materials. However, low-achieving students or those with limited computer skills can use the tutor's instructions. Despite the inclusion of listening tests, the primary objective of the site is not to assess students' listening proficiency. Rather, students can explore methods to enhance their listening abilities by engaging in a variety of pre-, while-, and post-listening activities.

This website possesses its own set of laws and regulations, and a considerable quantity of material is readily available for utilization. Resources for teachers and students to listen to a wide range can be very useful and can be used in Zoom lessons or ONLINE lessons. Topics can be easily modified depending on the complexity of the all-round exercise sequence. A podcast is an audio file that a student or reader can download onto their computer, phone, or MP3 player and listen to at their convenience. You can modify the files to make them run faster or slower, or to simply listen to a part of the program. Podcasts now cover a wide range of topics. Students have access to nearly 30 series that cover topics such as science, movies, history, teaching, language, and stories. There is something to suit everyone. You will find a list of some podcasts for English learners at <http://independentenglish.wordpress.com/podcasts>.

The majority of podcasts are available for free and can be found on the BBC Podcasts page, the Apple Podcast application (which is automatically installed on Apple devices), or through the iTunes Podcasts tab. Alternatively, a search on Google can prove to be beneficial. Occasionally, we encounter words during the lesson that may prove to be a bit challenging for both the teacher and the student to pronounce. This YouGlish page proves to be a valuable resource for enhancing the ability of students to access the internet and access the YouGlish page, thereby enabling them to listen to words with diverse accents.

Moreover, one has the option to view videos and peruse the subtitles. There has been a growing interest in pronunciation teaching and learning, given recent advances in technology. Due to these advances, we have seen the emergence of numerous applications and websites geared towards pronunciation. Levis stated that computers can provide personalized instruction, frequent practice through listening discrimination and focused repetition exercises, and automatic visual support. YouGlish, a website that uses YouTube videos to present target vocabulary through videos from a variety of genres, is an invaluable resource for English language learners to improve their pronunciation.

It is challenging for learners to comprehend or listen because they must swiftly distinguish speech sounds and retain them when hearing a word, phrase, or sentence. This is something that students can easily and naturally accomplish in their native tongue, but they are unable to do it in a foreign language when they begin learning it. Students take a long time to understand what they are learning since they are aware of the linguistic forms they are exposed to. This leads to misinterpretation or a complete failure of comprehension. Learning a foreign language requires students to be very attentive and creative. In order to decode the sequence of sounds they hear, they will need to practice their memory. Not all of the students are able to handle the challenges presented. They should be assisted by the teacher by making this activity easier and more engaging.

Additionally, any of these webpages may serve as an example assignment for an online course. This is possible if they will take into account the following three key elements that might guarantee the success of language learners' auding skill development:

- linguistic material for auding;
- the content of the material suggested for listening and comprehension;
- conditions in which the material is presented.

As educators, we should conduct needs analyses before providing listening resources based on students' interests and skill levels. All of these websites are reliable and engaging resources for both teachers and students.

Conclusion

Language instruction has advanced dramatically as a result of the integration of speaking and listening abilities through the use of digital tools and applications. These technologies give students compelling, adaptable, and interactive environments that mimic real-world communication situations. Learners can enhance their listening comprehension skills while practicing speaking using apps that offer features like interactive conversations, speech recognition, and real-time feedback. Platforms like podcasts, video conferencing tools, and language learning applications give students the chance to hear a variety of accents, speech patterns, and real-world conversations, which improves their comprehension and production of spoken language.

The capacity to customize the learning process is one of the biggest advantages of digital tools. By customizing their practice to fit their unique requirements, abilities, and interests, learners can increase the process's efficiency and motivation. Additionally, these resources promote self-directed learning by giving students the opportunity to practice both abilities at their own speed and get prompt, helpful feedback.

The limits of traditional classroom settings are also addressed by digital tools, which provide a wealth of practice possibilities, including role-playing scenarios, simulated conversations, and virtual chats with peers and native speakers around the world. By facilitating group interactions and cross-cultural exchanges in virtual settings, digital tools also promote collaborative learning. In addition to enhancing language proficiency, these exchanges boost students' self-assurance in everyday conversation. Digital tools promote a comprehensive approach to language learning that mirrors natural communication processes by integrating speaking and listening.

To sum up, digital tools and applications have shown to be quite helpful in incorporating language learning abilities and providing creative answers to the problems associated with language instruction. When used well, they produce learner-centered, immersive experiences that improve competency and get students ready for real-world communication in an increasingly interconnected world. By exposing students to a variety of dialects, speech rates, and situations, digital technologies greatly improve listening abilities.

By exposing students to realistic aural input, podcasts, films, and virtual simulations help them improve their comprehension of spoken language in a variety of contexts. Students can also practice speaking in a secure, accepting environment with the help of tools like AI chatbots and speech recognition applications. By giving learners instant feedback on their grammar, pronunciation, and fluency, these devices help them improve their speaking skills.

All things considered, digital tools and applications provide a revolutionary approach to incorporating language learning abilities, resolving the difficulties associated with conventional classroom instruction while encouraging genuine, purposeful language practice. In addition to improving language skills, these resources foster self-assurance, cultural sensitivity, and communication flexibility.

Digital technologies will play an increasingly important role in language instruction as they develop further, providing creative ways to close the gap between theory and practical application. Teachers may design dynamic, learner-centered learning environments that equip students for success in an increasingly interconnected and globalized world by skillfully utilizing these resources.

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